

Assessing the Effectiveness of Public Relations Strategies of the CBN during the Implementation of its Naira Redesign Policy in Nigeria

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Abstract

Crises require drastic measures that include communication to address issues arising from reputational damage and failure in social responsibility. The use of public relations is considered one of such ways to approach situations of that nature. During the implementation of Nigeria's Central Bank currency redesign policy, a series of unplanned aftereffects were recorded in the country. Cash shortage, fuel scarcity, among others, were just but few of the issues. Accordingly, there was a need to engage the people. Therefore, this study was conducted to assess the effectiveness of the PR strategies of the apex bank in the implementation of the naira redesign policy. The researchers relied on the survey research design and sampled 400 residents of different towns in the six area councils of the FCT. Of the 400 copies of the questionnaire that were administered, 374 were retrieved and found usable, amounting to a 93.5 percent response rate. Findings of the study showed that there was public relations-related communication from the apex bank during the implementation of the policy and that various communication avenues, such as TV/radio, newspapers/magazines, as well as the new media (through text messages) and social media, were used as avenues. However, the communication failed to be effective due to the absence of an empathetic tone in the efforts to engage the public. The researchers concluded that the bank failed to leverage communication to assuage the people in the implementation phase of its policy and recommended that there is a need to understand the importance of a people-led implementation campaign and consider effective engagements in the future.

Keywords: Crisis, Communication, Currency, Naira, Nigeria

Introduction

Communication is mostly intentional and used to convey meaningful messages or information between humans. Lack of communication or absence of it can lead to misunderstanding and then disagreements in any human society. It is against this backdrop that communication has been described as essential aspect of all human relationships without which a clear direction is not ascertained (Moore, 2023). The foregoing understandably underscores the importance of communication efforts in any human relationship or dealing. Aside providing the requisite mutual understanding for relationships to thrive, communication also helps strengthen the foundation upon which they are built, nourished or maintained over time.

In our modern world, communication is as important to organisations and institutions as much as it is to individual members of the society. The foregoing has been emphasised in the form that an organisation with talented personnel but without effective communication is defective and may produce little result (Vaughan, 2022). This also underscores the importance of communication in public relations (PR). Its importance stems from the numerous applications of relevance in an around the human society. This is significant because although diverse species of living things possess unique ways of communication, humans remain the only ones with mastered cognitive language of communication considered meaningful (Pagel, 2017).

According to Shah (2023) communication remains an integral part of PR because it is an important tool through which knowledge gap can be bridged, brand awareness created and built, and reputation managed for an organisation. Aside the use of communication to achieve these goals with the external population, it is seen as a key means through which the internal population can be engaged and motivated. In other words, communication is a key aspect of and organisation; be it growth efforts with respect to sales and goodwill or simply for passing information to staff. The communicative avenues create a way to ensure that there is proper exchange of information, thoughts, ideas and any other useful meaning.

PR is a necessity for public institutions; not just to announce decisions reached by the government but also the process of making policies (Çelebi, 2020). According to Martyniuk (2022) government can use PR to build support for initiatives and policies, and the target audience is the citizenry who most often need to hear the government's position and standpoint on several things. The act of providing necessary information to members of the public during the planning stage of policy is indeed a democratic practice. The expectation is that the government uses such avenues to seek, assess and adopt the favourable opinions of the public, who are most times the recipients of both the good and bad outcomes of a policy. The foregoing point has been buttressed that government communication about potential policy is arguably a democratic practice whereby the views and needs of the public can be sought on the policy matter (Gelders & Ihlen, 2010).

An important aspect of government PR or media relations is crisis management (Martyniuk, 2022). Though most definitions of crisis tilt towards sudden and negative events, it must be noted that human actions, such as inadequately communicated policy changes and actions, can trigger a crisis, which may spiral into other unpredicted matters and issues for a country. It is against this backdrop that crisis has been described as an occurrence based on an

unforeseen consequence of some event that had been considered as a potential risk (Posey & Wigmore, 2020). In a crisis, government PR is expected to focus on the provision of timely and accurate information to members of the public, and professionals whose speciality is PR are expected to manage media enquiries and strive to maintain public trust. Anything short of this can be considered a PR failure, which may harm the reputation of the government and its institutions.

The central bank of any nation is considered its apex bank and is, among other things, responsible for the management and control of the nation's financial architecture. In the same vein, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) is the apex financial institution in Nigeria, and part of its primary responsibility is to direct the supply of money. Another is to play an advisory role in respect of good policymaking in the financial sector of a country (Enang, 2022). More so, the apex bank is empowered by an act of parliament to issue, reissue, print and exchange currency notes and coins across Nigeria, and this is provided for in sections 2b, 17, and 18 of the CBN Act (Olabimtan, 2023). It must also be noted that the act also requires the CBN to seek and obtain the approval of the president of the Federal Republic of Nigeria before making the changes (Adegboyega, 2022). This implies that it is a government policy on the basis that an institution of government plans and executes the policy with approval from the head of government.

In October 2022, the CBN announced the redesign of three different notes that were in circulation in the country – namely N200, N500, and N1000 and same time informed Nigerians to deposit their old notes before the deadline of January 31, 2023, when the notes previously acceptable as legal tender would cease to enjoy the status. These issues generated a lot of crises as Nigerians became apprehensive, mainly arising from the scarcity of the notes following the deadline for implementation (Akpan, 2023; Arogbonlo, 2023; Ndujihe et al., 2023). It therefore called for communication from the government institution responsible for the policy and its implementation. This is where the issue of PR comes into play. The CBN was known to have reached the people in different ways using multiple platforms. Therefore, this study appraises the PR strategies deployed by the apex financial institution to gauge their effectiveness or otherwise. Notably, the study attempts to identify the PR strategy types, needs for the PR, and challenges in the implementation of the policy from the perspective of communication strategies deployed for PR.

The period was characterised by difficulties ranging from scarcity of both old and new notes, skyrocketed transportation costs and many more. Specifically, the period saw a rise in the cost of essential commodities required by Nigerians, with untold hardship on the civil servants (Okafor, 2023). According to Ighoroje, et al (2024), the redesign policy also hurt small and medium-scale enterprises, limiting their performance throughout the period considered as the implementation phase. The difficulties that accompanied the announcement by the apex bank elicited different reactions from the Nigerian public. The implication of this is that there was an urgent need for communication from the concerned authority. This called for concerted efforts of the apex banks through different means possible to assuage the public. Public relations is better imagined as a suitable option. This is based on the outcome of several studies that demonstrated the role of PR in crisis management (Babatunde, 2022; Oyewole, 2023; Ushie, 2021).

Despite these results, the CBN naira redesign policy implementation, seen a few months to the 2023 presidential election, presented unique challenges and created a multi-dimensional

crisis and reputational issues for the apex bank. This study therefore was conducted to assess the effectiveness of the PR strategies deployed by the bank in the policy implementation phase.

Statement of the Problem

The naira currency redesign initiative of the CBN generated a series of conflicts in Nigeria following the announcement by the apex financial institution that the old notes would cease to be legal tender accepted for financial transactions in the country. The issues around the policy generated both political and social crises. From the social angle, a section of Nigeria felt deceived by the government on the basis that the announcement that followed the policy was that there will be availability of the new notes – and the opposite was the case as they were subjected to hardship due to scarcity of both the old and new notes (Adegboruwa, 2023). From the political angle, the policy was seen as politics-motivated because it was introduced on the eve of an election year (Peterside, 2023). These colourations and dimensions made the situation complicated, putting the CBN in a difficult situation of having to provide clear communication within the period.

The CBN attempted to communicate with Nigerians during the period through different platforms – traditional media forms and new media. However, such moves have been criticised as insufficient. In addition, studies have shown that the introduction of policy may have caused untold hardship on the Nigerian population, who had to endure the period (Ani et al., 2024; Okafor, 2023). Additionally, questions have also been asked whether the CBN effectively communicated the goals, aims and process of the policy (Peterside, 2023). The confusion and numerous questions left unanswered provide the basis for this study. Therefore, this study attempts to appraise the PR strategies of the CBN with a view to determine their effectiveness during the naira redesign policy in Abuja.

Research Questions

1. What PR strategies were adopted by the CBN in the implementation phase of its naira redesign policy?
2. How effective were the PR strategies amid the naira redesign policy in Nigeria?

Conceptual Review

Public Relations

Public Relations (PR) refers to the techniques or set of strategies and techniques about the management of how information about an individual or organisation is disseminated to the public, especially the media (Hayes, 2023). In line with the foregoing definition, the media is also part of the public of an organisation. The primary objectives and goals of PR include public information dissemination, maintaining brand image, and positively framing negative events to minimise the fallout with the public. Avenues through which an organisation can take on its PR could be in the form of a news conference, press release, interviews with journalists, social media engagement and many others.

Another definition offered by The Economic Times sees PR as the strategies and methods used to control how information about a person or an organisation gets to the public, especially

the media. This definition shows that the media is also a public. Therefore, there is need to also control the type, amount, and angle of information allowed out into the hands of the media; that is one way PR is carried out in an organisation. PR can also be a strong tool talk to the public on issues that may be misconstrued. In this respect, PR is used to defray investor or public outcry as a response to a negative piece of information in the news to which they are exposed (Hayes, 2023).

A further definition sees PR as an organisational tool that makes use of sociological and psychological skills and knowledge to aid an organisation to take on a positive approach and thus present a positive image of itself and its activities to the public (Grimsley, 2021). The implication of the foregoing is that the organisation, while using PR, has an aim in mind; and that is to ensure that the public is made to see it in a positive light. A careful look at PR will reveal that it is of strategic communication process often deployed by organisation to develop positive relationships with the public and all other stakeholders, internal publics as well.

Naira Redesign Policy

The concept of policy is broad, but it is considered in this section in its simplest form. Policy can be seen as a regulation, law, voluntary practice, procedure, incentive of institutions of government and the government itself. According to Demir (2021) can be defined as the goals, actions, statements, and steps taken by the government towards the implementation of a solution. This implies that a policy is often made to proffer a solution to an identified problem or issue. In line with the foregoing, the government, through its institutions, often creates policies that could address loopholes in the general laws governing the country, and even others such as the appropriation. The government can be introduced to address a myriad of problems facing the country.

The concept has also been defined as a general guideline that offers clear direction to formulate specific programmes (Yigzaw, 2021). From this perspective, it is conceptualised as the course of action of government, official institutions, and other sectors, and may include goals, vision, plans, and principles that guide the activities of the different sectors of government and governance (Igun, 2011). The implication of the foregoing is that once government has vision and goals, they immediately turn such into policy documents to guide her in the implementation of such plans, goals, and vision (as the case may be). Therefore, when the government conceptualise the vision, to stop geometric population growths, they immediately introduce the birth control policies. In relations to that, if the vision is to be self-sufficient in food production, the best thing to do is to develop agricultural policies that will encourage able bodied members of the society to go into farming. This cuts across all sectors of the life of a nation.

The CBN is not new to naira redesign, as the apex bank has always introduced currencies at different points in history. One that easily comes to mind was the redesign of the N100 bill in 2014 to mark the nation's centenary celebrations (Usman, 2014). Nigeria celebrated its centenary as a nation in the year following the 1914 amalgamation of the then Southern and Northern Protectorates. However, the most recent was that of 2022 when the bank announced that it had introduced a new design for the N200, N500, and N1000 bills of the legal tender used in Nigeria. The redesign, the apex bank reported, was based on the request by the Federal Government (Ejekwonyilo, 2023). The deadline was fixed for December 2022 as the time the old notes will

cease to be accepted as legal tender in the country, and this generated so much conflict in the land.

Part of the reasons adduced by the CBN for the redesign of the naira were, among other things enable the bank to take control of the currency in circulation, manage inflation, combat currency counterfeiting and ransom payment. These were the main reasons to introduce the new banknotes. As for the first reason adduced by the apex bank, it is seen from the perspective that super rich and influential individuals have carried out currency fraud and made it their primary source of income. Certain elements are known to stash plenty naira notes they have stolen; and so the policy was targeted at such a category of persons, leaving them no choice but to release the cash they kept in captivity (Osadebe, 2022). The second one has to do with lowering the inflation rate. Though this has been argued by several scholars as being a reason for further weakening of the currency (KMPG, as cited in Balogun, 2023; Idowu et al., 2022; Onukwue, 2022), the CBN believed otherwise and went further to implement.

Another goal the policy hoped to achieve was to control the amount of money in circulation. The apex had hoped that by introducing the new notes and a deadline for depositing the old banknotes in deposit money banks (DMBs), it would succeed in introducing control measures to tame the growing circulation of the naira and thereby save the economy from imminent dangers. Following the several scenarios of political colouration and the difficulties the change created in the country, it cannot be said to have achieved this aim after all. There were reports of hoarding of the notes even with the policy in full force in its implementation in the country. It was a breaking point due to the socio-economic implications of the times.

Finally, the currency redesign was introduced to curtail the growing kidnapping for ransom that was rampant in the country at the time the policy was designed and introduced. In recent times, Nigeria had battled insurgency in the North East, armed banditry in parts of North Central and North West, and militancy in the Niger Delta region. However, a thing of note here is that all of these insecurity problems have something in common; they culminated in the abduction of persons and the ransom demand. To deal a heavy blow to such illicit business, the CBN redesigned the currency; a situation that brought about scarcity of cash, as the few bank notes available could not circulate. To some extent, this aim was achieved as kidnapping reduced while the naira redesign crisis raged (Adesina, as cited in Adeyemo, 2023; Oluwafemi, 2023). The foregoing does not reflect the position of all policy watchers, as others simply believe the policy did not achieve much in respect of kidnapping for ransom in the country (Sunday, 2023).

Literature Review

According to Hayes (2023), PR has proved to be a good tool used for corporate communication efforts. This is even though the two concepts are distinct. It also implies that in the corporate world, PR is one of the tools explored by organisations and institutions to communicate with their publics, internal and external. PR does a lot for organisations in modern times. Sherman (2019) lends credence that in any human organisation, the PR team is needed to perform multiple functions; some of which are relationship management, crisis management, resource management, and image management. This stresses the importance of PR to an organisation. Santas (2020), is of the view that communication is at the centre of every human activity in several organisations.

According to Pulse Marketing, there are five components of PR strategy, which include corporate communications, media relations, community relations, crisis management, and events management. These five are referred to as working parts of the PR architecture required by an organisation that intends to build a positive image in the eyes of the stakeholders or the public. According to Marta (2023), a crisis often tests the viability of the PR strategy, but no matter what, during a crisis, the PR unit's main goal should be to inform all interested stakeholders about the current situation, potential risks, and the planned actions. An essential aspect of the strategy in a crisis is the first message that will be sent out to the public.

When it comes to a crisis, a particular strategy or PR plan may appear defective, and this is where creativity comes in, as the PR experts may need to step up their game and do more. Different authors with their unique and varying perspectives as to what makes up a communication strategy that works well in a crisis. Three of such have been identified as communicate, communicate, communicating, being caring and responsible, as well as speaking with one voice (Proverbs, n.d.). The importance of constant communication efforts amid a crisis as part of PR strategy is emphasised because the public deserves to be engaged throughout. Another is to show care and take responsibility. Here, the organisation or the spokesperson must avoid shifting blame and accept responsibility. Above all, different individuals representing the organisation must harmonise their thoughts and responses to speak with one voice and must not be seen to be communicating different messages.

Reputation management is also one of PR's core goals. Reputation management is based in PR. In other words, PR is considered the foundation upon which reputation management stands. This is based on the notion that it is a difficult task to build and maintain positive reputation for an organisation without a strong PR strategy. Credibility and trust reposed on an institution by members of the public often takes root in PR efforts, and these are essentials in reputation management, which itself is an extension of PR. In any serious human organisation that prioritises PR, reputation management efforts, aspects of PR can be used to identify and address potential issues before they snowball into major problems or crises. To spearhead this crisis is the PR officer or the communication officer of an organisation (Santas, 2020).

In a study conducted by Ushie (2021), part of the findings is that PR is effective in crisis management. This was based on the survey results, which demonstrate that 60% of respondents who took the survey agreed with the notion. This is also consistent with the position of Babatunde (2022) that social media has become an effective tool in crisis communication management. Since managing a crisis effectively requires forethought, PR crisis management becomes useful in that regard (Muse & Motif, 2022). It is something of worth that organisations set in motion all necessary mechanisms that can activate crisis management PR for the overall good of the reputation of the organisation. It is so because upon such rests the survival and failure of an organisation. It is on this premise that most organisations spend millions of dollars consulting PR firms to handle their reputation management (Santas, 2014).

Several problems have been identified as posing a great hindrance to PR practice, especially in the 21st century. According to Johnston (2019), these challenges of PR could be in the form of corporate credibility problems, multiple channels noise, measuring the impact of social media, and two-way PR. Establishing credibility for an organisation is no mean task, and it is seen as one challenge faced by PR in modern times. Another one is that of noise from multiple

channels, and this is due to the multiple channels of communication available to the PR experts – radio, television, and social media. These create a challenge as the PR team needs to draft specific-tailored messages sometimes to cater for the information needs of each of the channel users. The challenge of having to measure the impact of social media is another one; as it is not simple for an organisation or its PR team to take on without the services of a third-party tracking programme such as Adobe Analytics, Hootsuite etc. The last one is two-way PR that requires constant monitoring of messages in the form of feedback from the public of the organisation, preparatory to altering messages to cater for a segment of the public.

There are specific empirical studies that focused on the use of PR strategies for different situations. Researchers and scholars have especially devoted time to understanding crises within the corporate world. Some others also gave attention to the implementation of the policy and the communication strategy adopted. Some of such studies are reviewed in this study. Okure, et al. (2024) conducted a study titled "Crisis communication strategy of select banks during the Naira redesign policy in Nigeria" and was conducted to gauge the perceptions of customers as to the consistency of message dissemination by select banks during the naira redesign period. The findings of the study showed that select Nigerian banks did not provide adequate and regular information to their customers during the period of the implementation of the naira redesign policy of the CBN.

Dada (2023) conducted a study on "Currency redesign policy implementation: Implications for industrial performance in Nigeria", primarily to investigate the impact the newly introduced policy has on the performance of industries in the country. The researcher selected 514 MSMLEs across five states in the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. The study showed that food manufacturing, agro-based enterprises and agribusinesses, paints production, textile and clothing, and plastic production were some of the types of businesses engaged in enterprise operations. It was also revealed in the study that the policy had both negative and positive effects on the industries and small businesses.

Similarly, the study on the "Effect of naira redesign policy on welfare of civil servants: A study of Abakaliki metropolis" was conducted by Okafor (2023) to ascertain the effect of the policy on the financial welfare of the public servants and also investigate the challenges of the policy on the social welfare of civil servants. The findings of the study showed that the naira redesign came with its peculiar negative consequences as residents of Abakaliki were traumatised due to the inconveniences they suffered on account of the lack of access to the redesigned bank notes, and even the old ones being replaced. Other psychologically draining scenarios include long queues at bank ATMs and the associated social discomfort on the public servants who had to endure the period. Furthermore, the researcher revealed that significant costs accompanied the announcement of the implementation of the policy, as food prices, transportation costs, and office and home supply costs skyrocketed.

Theoretical Framework

This theory, "the framing effect," suggests that people make decisions based on how an issue is framed and presented to them rather than the facts therein. It is said to be a cognitive default to make choices more positively framed or presented (Dolan, 2023). Put differently, people are likely to go with a choice that was presented in the best manner possible to the point that it captures their minds. Another name for framing effect is framing bias, and it refers to a type of

cognitive bias that speaks to a person's decision simply being influenced by the presentation or framing of the message (Cheprasov, 2022). It is a superb explanation to a situation where individuals are faced with the choice of deciding based on account of the facts presented in some ways.

This theory applies to this study because it captures the explanation of the effect of frames assigned to issues presented to the people. It could be about the use of different media forms: print, broadcast, and new media. These media are also avenues for PR efforts of organisations and institutions. In this study, the PR effort by the CBN amid the implementation of the naira redesign policy is the focus. Consequent upon the foregoing, this theory explains the frames ascribed to the different messages around the policy implementation during the period. This supports the fundamentals of writing for PR as the tone of the message determines the receptiveness of the customers. Accordingly, the tone is set by framing of the messages, and so this theory explains how the frames were assigned to ascertain whether such affected the people who happened to be the target of the messages drafted to provide adequate information amid the implementation of the naira redesign policy in Nigeria.

Method

The study is a survey design based on the desire of researchers to expand the scope of individuals from whom data were gathered for the study. The population of the study comprised members of the public, particularly those in the six (6) area councils of the federal capital territory, Abuja. The territory was considered for this study because it is the location of the headquarters of the Central Bank of Nigeria, the custodian of the naira redesign policy as implemented in 2022/2023, which is within the period under review in this study. The estimated figure of the population of the FCT is put at 3,067,500 based on records of NBS, as seen in the city population. The sample size of 400 was derived from the population, relying on Taro Yamane's sample size determination formula given below:

$$\text{Eq. 1: } n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

In line with the study design, a stratified sampling method was adopted to identify towns in various area councils for the study. Accordingly, the stratification yielded major towns being the major residential areas in each area council, and these are Abaji, Jabi, Kubwa, Zuba, Kude, and Kwali. The questionnaire happened to be the primary instrument of data collection. It was designed to elicit demographic and variable enquiry data. The instrument was subjected to face validity by communication experts in the Department of Mass Communication, Nasarawa State University. After the validation, research ethics were considered with an ethical statement included in the instrument. Respondents were assured of their anonymity and made to sign off willingness to take the survey. They were also informed of their right to willingly participate and withdraw at any time they deemed without any liability to them. Method of administering the instrument was on a personal basis, as the researchers administered copies directly to the respondents.

Results

The data presented hereunder is based on the perception of the members of the public residing

Figure 1. Gender of Respondents

Source: *Field survey, 2024*

Data in Figure 1 above demonstrated that 232 male respondents took the survey, and by implication, more of the persons are male adults. Furthermore, the data above is an implication that both men and women in affected communities in the FCT took the survey and shared their perceptions.

Figure 2. Age distribution of respondents

Source: *Field survey, 2024*

As seen in Figure 2 above, data indicated that the individuals between the ages of 31 and 45 make up the majority of those who took the survey. It was demonstrated that members of communities are of age to take the survey.

Figure 3. Educational qualification of respondents

Source: *Field survey, 2024*

Data in the figure 3 indicate that the community members in the FCT have the educational qualifications to take the survey.

Figure 5. Occupation of respondents

Source: *Field survey, 2024*

Occupation of the residents of the FCT who took the survey demonstrates that most of them are public servants who understand the naira redesign policy and its implementation.

Table 1: Knowledge of CBN naira redesign policy

Variable	Frequency	Percentages
Adequate	123	33

None	97	26
Not sure	116	31
Cannot say	38	10
Total	374	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

As seen in the data in table 1 above, 33 percent of respondents said they have adequate knowledge of the naira redesign policy of the CBN. This is an indication that the respondents in the FCT have adequate knowledge of the naira redesign policy though some were not sure of what it entails.

Table 2: Recall of events that characterise the policy implementation

Variable	Frequency	Percentages
Scarcity of both old and new notes	224	60
Fuel scarcity	19	5
Hunger and starvation	26	7
All of the above	97	26
None of the above	8	2
Total	374	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 data that during the period within which the policy was implemented, challenges such as scarcity of both old and new notes, fuel scarcity (energy crisis), and hunger in addition to starvation were some of the issues. The implication of the above is that respondents can recall some of the events that characterised the period of the naira redesign policy implementation.

Table 3: Communication amid the crisis

Variable	Frequency	Percentages
Definitely	266	71
Not at all	64	17

Cannot say	26	7
Not sure	18	5
Total	374	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Data in Table 3 showed that 71 percent of respondents agreed that there was communication amid the crisis. This is an indication, as revealed by the majority of the respondents, that indeed, there was communication amid the naira crisis initiated by the CBN in the FCT.

Table 4: Ways through which the message was received

Variable	Frequency	Percentages
Television/radio	90	24
Newspaper/magazine	18	5
Social media	97	26
Text messages	7	2
All of the above	124	33
None of the above	38	10
Total	374	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

As seen in table 4 above, residents received messages through various channels. However, data in the table demonstrate that majority respondents were exposed to messages about the policy on radio and televisions and this makes up 24 percent of respondents. Furthermore, 33 percent of them alluded to seeing messages through the various channels such as text messages, social media, newspaper/magazine, and radio/TV.

Table 5: Prominent features in the use of social media

Variable	Frequency	Percentages
Facebook	45	12
WhatsApp	19	5

X [Formerly Twitter]	64	17
All of the above	167	45
None	79	21
Total	374	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The data in Table 5 above social media platforms were greatly utilised during the naira redesign policy implementation in Abuja. Based on the notion that 45 percent of respondents used Facebook, WhatsApp X (formerly known as Twitter) was identified as prominently utilised in respect of social media use during the period.

Table 6: Notion that CBN communication on policy informed a change of perception

Variable	Frequency	Percentages
Strongly support	71	19
Support	52	14
Strongly oppose	180	48
Oppose	71	19
Total	374	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 6 data in show 48 percent of respondents opposing the notion that CBN communication on policy informed a change of perception. This implies a strong opposition to the notion that CBN communication on policy informed a change of perception.

Table 7: Communication tone suggestive of empathy

Variable	Frequency	Percentages {%}
Definitely	71	19
Not at all	135	36
Not sure	116	31

Cannot say	52	14
Total	374	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The data in Table 7 shows that 36 percent claimed that the tone of communication did not suggest any form of empathy. Therefore, the tone of the CBN's messages to the Nigerian public showed no empathy.

Table 8: Communication of CBN improved perception of apex bank

Variable	Frequency	Percentages
Strongly disagree	71	19
Disagree	187	50
Strongly agree	64	17
Agree	52	14
Total	374	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Implication of data in table 8 above is that there was no improvement in the perception of the apex bank as per communication amid the implementation of the naira redesign policy in Abuja-FCT.

Discussion of Findings

This study gauged the perception of members of the public, that was composed of residents of the six area councils in Abuja-FCT. It was revealed that there is some level of knowledge of the naira redesign policy by the CBN. Residents could also recall some of the events that characterised the policy implementation phase of the CBN's naira redesign. Accordingly, the study showed that within the period, there were cases of scarcity of the old and new notes, fuel scarcity, as well as hunger and starvation in the country. This is supported by the literature of the study conducted, with findings showing that Nigerians faced several challenges occasioned by the sudden implementation of the policy, chief of which was the scarcity of the naira notes (Adegboyega & Izuako, 2023; Awi, 2023; Monye, 2024). The hardship created by the scarcity was enough to cause bad publicity for the apex bank and a threat to the national pride of citizens (Okoronkwo, 2023).

The study also showed in its findings that there was communication from the apex bank during the implementation of the naira redesign policy. Members of the public were exposed to

such communication of messages through radio/TV, newspaper/magazine, social media, and text messages. This also mirrors findings of another study, where findings showed the use of emails, text messages and other new media and ICT channels (Ushie, 2021). In the study, the researcher attempted to gauge the perceptions of the respondents as to the communication channels suggested as tools for crisis management. Similarly, earlier studies also identified mass media forms of radio/TV, newspaper and magazine as effective PR channels (Adeniyi, 2016). In the study, the researcher identified several organisations like Dangote, GT Bank, Arik Air, Diamond (Now Access) Bank, and Stanbic IBT Bank that utilised different channels for PR and advertising. Related studies also found the use of media channels by DUFIL Nigeria in the management of the 2004 Indomie poison scare (Harold & Onyekosor, 2024).

Further findings of the study also revealed that there was prominent use of social media platforms for communication as members of the public were exposed to messages through Facebook, X and WhatsApp within the period. Findings of the study conducted by Olley and Orhewere (2023) buttressed the foregoing. The researchers showed evidence that Nigerians discussed the naira redesign policy across various social media platforms, with some pointing to sentiment analysis. This also aligns with the study conducted by Oladapo and Akinbo (2024) on the use of different social media platforms as a means of engagement and discourse by Nigerians on the policy. This might imply a greater use of the platforms as a means of engagement on issues relating to the implementation within the period under review. On a general note, PR increasingly leveraged social media as critical channels (Awofadeju & Ewuola, 2019; Pranta et al., 2023).

Findings of the study also showed that communication from the apex bank had no direct impact as per change of perception of the role played by the institution in the suffering of the people while the implementation of the policy lasted. Based on the perception of members of the public, messages of the CBN to which they were exposed showed no tone that depicted empathy. Therefore, study revealed that the communication did not improve the perception of the bank among the people in Abuja-FCT. This is suggestive of a communication and PR defective outcome as also suggested by Eromosele (2023), that the apex seemingly never had a communication strategy to engage the people of Nigeria amid the naira redesign policy implementation phase.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

This study concludes that there was communication through various PR strategies and communication channels, but there was no impact due to the tone and drive of the communication. The rationale for communication in crisis, among others, is to ensure that the public is armed with adequate information to enable them to make informed decisions and also to have a full grasp of issues occurring at the time. During the implementation and the crisis that accompanied the announcements and related actions of the apex, there was a need for communications that assuaged the people and provided some empathy. In addition, there was a dire need for explanations on the positives, but the CBN communication throughout the period was that of how the policy must go on with the people put in the frame of providing support, whether they agreed with the content and aftereffects of the policy.

Recommendations

The researchers recommend that:

1. The bank must understand the importance of a people-championed cause and policy. This implies that future policies must be explained to the public through open communication to ensure that they are convinced to provide maximum support to its draft and implementation process.
2. Policy implementation must also consider the untold hardship. This can be achieved even in the formulation stage, where measures are considered to cushion the effect of any form of hardship that may arise, as seen during the implementation of the naira redesign policy in Nigeria.

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